

Elite lines for rainfed lowlands in North Bihar, India

B.N. Singh and S.P. Sahu, Plant Breeding Department, Rajendra Agricultural University, Pusa (Samastipur), Bihar 848125, India

North Bihar, a medium-deep waterlogged area, is planted primarily to rainfed lowland rice. But in years with poor rainfall, drought occurs at vegetative or reproductive stages. Rice tungro virus also causes major yield losses in some years, bacterial leaf blight occurs sporadically, and brown spot and narrow brown leaf spot are severe in years of poor rainfall.

Farmers usually grow traditional tall, lodging-susceptible, and photoperiod-sensitive varieties that can yield at least

1.5 t/ha under stress. Seedlings are planted after the onset of rains in mid-June, and transplanted 15-60 d after seeding, after water accumulates in the field. One or two applications of urea is topdressed when water level lessens in the field before flowering. Plant protection is minimal.

Efforts are underway to select an improved nonlodging plant type, 150-160 d duration, photoperiod-insensitive, limited elongation, early seedling vigor, and intermediate height (120-130 cm). Evaluation of lines and segregating generations from national and international sources is in progress. Both pedigree and bulk breeding methods are being used. The segregating generations are grown under shallow and waterlogged rainfed lowland conditions

in alternate years to select desirable types.

The major problem in improved photoperiod-insensitive varieties is sheath rot disease, maybe due to variation in seedling age, seeding time, or cooler temperature at flowering. Zn deficiency in the seedling stage as well as after transplanting have also become major constraints in recombinant lines.

During 1985 wet season, when the water level reached 80 cm, 154 entries in 6 replicated yield trials and 305 lines in 2 observational nurseries were evaluated (see table). Yield varied; it was a maximum 2 t/ha in both insensitive and sensitive groups. The high-yielding entries will be further evaluated in yield trials, for use in hybridization programs. □

Elite lines that performed well in replicated trials and observational nurseries. Bihar, India, 1985 wet season.

	Entries tested (no.)	Designation
<i>Trial</i>		
IRRSWYN (M)	28	BRB8-2B-74, BR 222-B-358, Matcandu
UVT-4 (DRR)	31	IET8005 (RP1486-834-1), IET7598 (RP1486-833-1)
UVT-3 (DRR)	20	IET7520 (RP1854-566-1-1-1), IET8033 (RAU49-54-1-2), IET8611 (MTU 6861)
UVT-5 (State)	26	TCA808, TCA48, TCA148-3
PVT-5 (State)	25	IET7970 (TCA80-4), SBIR38-140-2, SBIR38-148-3
UVT-4 (State)	24	IET6696 (IR42), BIET1165 (RAU77-1), IR3646-9-3-1
<i>Nurseries</i>		
IRRSWON	203	B4259-48-1-3-1-3, CN505-5-3-1, Dud Kalash, IR20880-25-P3, IR21064-48-2-1E-P1, Leuang Yai 148, Matcandu
LLSN	102	CN571-236-15-1, CN570-661-48-3, OR611-8, OR620-17, OR620-52, OR621-6, CN706-2-26, CN569-705-8-1, CN566-915-63, CN363-3, CN578-190-7-1, CN567-682-25-3, CN580-869-42-3

ADT37 released for Tamil Nadu

A. P. M. K. Soundararaj, V. Sivasubramanian, and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TRRI), Aduthurai 612101, India

BG367-4, an International Rice Testing Program introduction evaluated in Tamil Nadu since 1980, was released in May 1987 as ADT37 for general cultivation in the first crop season (Apr-Jul sowing).

Mean grain yield was 6.3 t/ha, more than that of IR50, ADT36, and TKM9 (Table 1). ADT37 yielded 4.9 t/ha in

multilocation trials, and 6.2 t/ha in adaptive research trials (Table 2).

ADT37 is moderately tillering. Its high yield potential is mainly due to high panicle weight, in turn due to high number of grains per panicle. Grains are short and bold with white rice; milling recovery is 71%. Cooking quality is highly preferred.

ADT37 is resistant to leaf yellowing disease, blast, brown spot, brown planthopper, and green leafhopper; and moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight, rice tungro virus, gall midge, and leafhopper. It is highly suitable for direct seeding. □

Table 1. Performance of ADT37 at TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1983-86.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle wt (g)	Grains (no./panicle)
ADT37	6.3	106	436	1.62	82
IR50	5.3	103	542	1.21	68
ADT36	5.7	108	510	1.35	73
TKM9	6.1	110	496	1.40	68

Table 2. Performance of ADT37 in trials in Tamil Nadu, India, 1985-86.

Trial	Locations (no.)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		
		ADT37	IR50	TKM9
Multilocation	6	4.9	4.2	4.7
Adaptive research	57	6.2	5.9	5.7